

ECONOMIC VIABILITY OF RICE FARMING IN BHADRAK DISTRICT OF ODISHA: A SOCIO-ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The majority of people in India live in villages and depend on agriculture for their livelihood. 17% of the GDP comes from this sector. Because of natural disasters and market swings, farmers' circumstances remain precarious despite economic and technological progress. News of farmer suicides in various regions of the nation during drought years emphasizes the consequences of this diversity. The primary source of income for the residents of Bhadrak district is agriculture, with paddy accounting for approximately 94% of the total cultivable area and serving as the primary crop grown during the Kharif season. A farmer's socioeconomic status can be determined by a number of factors, such as their education, income, expenditures, savings, land ownership, livestock status, debt, and more. The current study intends to examine the socioeconomic analysis of rice farmers in the Bhadrak district of Odisha. This study is based on a primary survey from 400 Farmers are selected through multistage random sampling. The data reveals trends, such as higher percentages of illiteracy and lower educational attainment among older age groups and a relatively small number of respondents possessing a degree across all age brackets. A stark imbalance is present with males and females, indicating male dominance in farming practices. Most farmers pertain to Kharif season cultivation while involving both Kharif and Rabi seasons. The data clearly indicates a predominance of Kharif season cultivation, with nearly 70% of the cases, underscoring its significance in the agricultural cycle. Farmers unanimously agreed on the necessity of cultivating rice, underscoring its importance despite the challenges faced. The present study suggested that to make seeds available for farming, decrease the price of seeds, improve irrigation facilities, provide crop insurance, and provide subsidies for seeds and fertilizer, etc.

Keywords: Socio-Economic, Rice Farmers, Land holdings, Literacy, Cropping intensity

1. INTRODUCTION:

Rice is the world's most significant food crop; hence it deserves special recognition among cereals. This is farmed across 155 million ha in 114 countries and is the most eaten food item, accounting for 31% of total calorie requirements (Mathur and Krishnaiah, 1996; Pillai, 1996). Rice is the primary cereal food grain of nearly one billion people in India, the world's most populous country, and the demand for rice in India is always increasing as the population grows. Rice per capita availability in India fell from 133 to 122 kg per year between 1989 and 2003 (FAOSTAT Database, 2004). Increased production must be done in the face of a dwindling and deteriorating resource base such as land, water, labour, and other inputs, all while preserving environmental quality.

In Odisha, rice is the most significant cereal, serving as the people's basic diet, and the majority of agricultural methods revolve on it. Rice yield in the state is unchanged, and the area under this primary food crop has shrunk dramatically during the last 25 years. Although the state's anticipated rice requirement is less than one-fifth of the total. Due to extensive conversion of paddy lands for other crops or residential usage, the area used for rice cultivation has decreased, resulting in an annual increase in the shortfall in rice production. In order to address the progression of vulnerability in coastal blocks in the Bhadrak district of Odisha, the socioeconomic vulnerability index (SEVI) was created. The district of Bhadrak is thought to be among the state's most susceptible regions to strong tropical cyclones. Agriculture's backbone is its rural population. The main occupation of those living in rural areas is growing crops. Determining the economic viability of rice cultivation in the Bhadrak district of Odisha is the aim of this study. Residents of the district own a little amount of land, and their earnings from non-farm and agricultural pursuits are not enough to meet their basic need.

2. Review of Literature:

The Literature Review consists of multiple studies focusing on the socio-economic impacts of agriculture, with particular attention to rice farming, natural farming, and the role of agricultural technologies. Each study examines different geographical locations and farming practices while highlighting key challenges, opportunities, and recommendations for improving agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

M.O. Onich et al. (2021) investigates "the effects of COVID-19 on the socio-economic livelihood of household rice farmers in Obubra Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria". The study highlights how the pandemic adversely affected small-scale rice farmers

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by reducing agricultural income, limiting access to financing, and disrupting farming activities due to lockdown restrictions. The research, based on a multi-stage sampling approach of 125 respondents, reveals that most rice farmers rely on small farm sizes and family labor, with limited access to financial support. The study recommends that farmers receive proper guidance on COVID-19 protocols to ensure safer agricultural practices while addressing key issues such as transportation and extension services.

Sharma Komal et al. (2024) explores the socio-economic status and challenges faced by farmers practicing natural farming in Himachal Pradesh, India. Natural farming emphasizes organic inputs and biodiversity while avoiding synthetic chemicals. The study, conducted in Kangra and Solan districts with 120 farmers, shows that most practitioners are small-scale farmers. The findings indicate that while natural farming has environmental benefits, the main challenges include labor-intensive processes, a lack of skilled workers, high labor costs, and insufficient market intelligence. To encourage more farmers to switch to natural farming, the report recommends establishing awareness campaigns, specialized marketplaces, and certification and financial assistance.

Jagdeep and Mamata (2024) examines “the socio-economic impacts of agricultural technologies on farmers' livelihoods in India”. The research highlights how farmers face challenges such as inadequate mechanization, limited irrigation, and high input costs despite working hard to sustain food production. The study, conducted across 32 districts in three states with 1,440 participants, finds that adopting agricultural technologies positively impacts farmers' income and productivity. The study concludes that technological advancements play a crucial role in improving efficiency and sustainability in agriculture.

The socioeconomic aspects impacting the use of Integrated Crop Management (ICM) technology for rice production and agribusiness sustainability are examined by Tintin Febrianti et al. (2024). In order to evaluate the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and technology adoption, the study uses multiple linear regression analysis and surveys and structured interviews with thirty rice farmers. The results show that farmers' readiness to embrace ICM technology is highly influenced by factors such as age, education, land size, and farming experience. But not all farmers adhere to the suggested practices while implementing new agricultural technologies. In order to promote the adoption of sustainable farming practices, the study highlights the necessity of improved education and training initiatives.

According to Kelvin Anene et al. (2024), the socioeconomic traits of Nigerian rice producers are the main focus. In addition to noting that women make up the majority of rice farmers, it draws attention to demographic characteristics like the prevalence of young farmers between the ages of 31 and 40. According to the study, in order to guarantee long-term sustainability, efforts should be taken to involve young people in rice production and to encourage male farmers to take an active role in the crop. The study intends to improve rice productivity and help small-scale farmers' livelihoods by tackling socioeconomic constraints.

The collection of studies provides a comprehensive analysis of the socio-economic dynamics affecting farmers across different regions. Common themes emerge, such as the importance of financial support, technology adoption, market accessibility, and labor challenges. While agricultural advancements and natural farming practices offer significant benefits, systemic challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, labor shortages, and financial constraints remain critical barriers. The studies collectively emphasize the need for policy interventions, improved extension services, and farmer education programs to drive sustainable agricultural development and improve livelihoods.

3.Objective of the Study:

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

- To investigate the socio-economic analysis of rice farmers in Bhadrak district of Odisha.

4.Research Methodology:

The current study was carried out in the Bhadrak district of Odisha state. They prominently and actively participate in a variety of farming chores, contributing to their household economics. The study used a multi-stage simple random sampling technique to choose blocks, panchayats, villages, and farmers, taking into account the task's magnitude as well as the time and resources available. The Bhadrak district statistics were utilized to construct a list of all the community development blocks, as well as the number of farmers with the highest rice output. One coastal community development block, Basudevpur, was chosen for the study over the other seven because it had the most farmers and produced the most rice. The Basudevpur block headquarters supplied a list of all villages, including the number of farmers and the greatest rice yield. As a result, five villages—Sugo, Sugo Patna, Kusunibindha, Kanjikhia, and Kalyanpur—were randomly selected to ensure that the study was thorough. A baseline survey was undertaken in each of the selected villages, and a list of farmers was compiled, together with information regarding their cultivated and rice-

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producing lands. A total of 400 farmers were drawn at random from the village list, and in the end, 80 farmers from Sugo village, 80 farmers from Sugo Patna village, 80 farmers from Kusunibindha village, 80 farmers from Kanjikhia village, and 80 farmers from Kalyanpur village were selected as interview respondents. The field surveys were conducted in 2023 and 2024. Rice production statistics for the study areas' primary crops were collected throughout both the kharif and Rabi seasons. The primary data for the study were gathered through personal interviews with randomly selected respondents utilizing a research questionnaire. The primary data included information such as educational status, asset position, cropping pattern, availability of resources such as land, labour, capital, machine, and animal power, crop income, and so on. The acquired data was tabulated to facilitate analysis and interpretation. Averages and percentages were calculated when needed. In many circumstances, simple tabular analysis met the study's objectives.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The economic sustainability of rice growing in Bhadrak district, Odisha, may be assessed from a socioeconomic standpoint by considering major elements such as production costs, yield, market circumstances, government regulations, and farmers' socioeconomic position. Bhadrak district is one of Odisha's most renowned rice-producing districts, with agriculture playing an important role in the rural economy. A variety of factors influence these farmers' socioeconomic level, including age, education, family structure, and resource availability.

Table No.-1: Socio-Economic status of the Farmers:

SL NO.	Independent variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	Less than 30	9	2.3
		31-40	74	18.5
		41-50	176	44
		51-60	101	25.3
		More than 61	40	10
2	Gender	Male	353	88.3
		Female	47	11.7
3	Education	Illiterate	163	40.8
		Primary	96	24
		Upper primary	93	23.3
		Secondary	24	6
		Higher Secondary	18	4.5
		Degree	6	1.5
4	Marital status	Married	390	97.5
		Unmarried	6	1.5
		Window	4	1
5	Caste	UR	88	22
		OBC/SEBC	264	66
		SC	43	10.8
		ST	5	1.3

Source: Field Survey

The table shows the farmers' socioeconomic position, as well as the frequencies and percentages that correspond to it. The tables include data on age distribution, gender, education level, marital status, and caste. The age group is divided into five categories, with the majority (44%) falling into the 41-50 age range. The gender distribution shows a much higher proportion of males (88.3%) than females (11.7%). Education levels vary, with a large proportion (40.8%) being illiterate and only a small number (1.5%) holding a degree. Marital status implies that most people (97.5%) are married. Finally, caste distribution shows that the majority (66%) are OBC/SEBC, followed by UR (22%), SC (10.8%), and ST (1.3%).

Table no. -2: Houses of the farmers:

House of the Farmer	Frequency	Percentage
Kuccha house	62	15.5
Semi pucca house	177	44.3
pucca house	98	24.5
Indira/Pradhan Mantri awas house	63	15.8

Source: Field Survey

The table shows data on the types of dwellings occupied by farmers, which are divided into four categories: Kuccha houses, Semi-pucca houses, Pucca houses, and Indira/Pradhan Mantri Awas buildings. It shows the frequency and percentage distribution of each home type. Kuccha dwellings, which are usually composed of temporary materials, account for 15.5% (62 households). Semi-pucca dwellings, which have partial durability, make up the largest category at 44.3% (177 families). Pucca dwellings, built with permanent materials, account for 24.5% (98 households). Finally, 15.8% (63 households) live in government-sponsored Indira or Pradhan Mantri Awas homes.

Table no. -3: Nature of Operational Holdings of farmers:

Nature and operational holding	Frequency	percentage
Wholly owned	197	49.3
wholly leased in holdings	135	33.8
partly owned and partly leased in	68	17

Source: Field survey

The table divides operational holdings into three categories: entirely owned, wholly leased-in, and partially owned and partly leased-in. The largest group is wholly held holdings, which account for 197 cases and 49.3% of the total. There are 135 fully leased-in holdings, accounting for 33.8% of the total. The smallest group is partly owned and partly leased-in holdings, which includes 68 examples and accounts for 17% of the total. This distribution

shows that approximately half of the operating holdings are entirely owned, with the rest split between wholly leased-in and mixed ownership structures.

Table no. 4: Farmer's amount land utilized:

Amount of land utilized	Frequency	Percent
Less than 1 hectare	120	30
1-2 hectare	190	47.5
4-10 hectare	90	22.5

Source: Field Survey

The table shows data on land utilization categorized by land size. It has three land size ranges: less than one hectare, one to two hectares, and and four to ten hectares. The associated frequencies represent the number of occurrences in each group, with 120 for less than 1 hectare, 190 for 1-2 hectares, and 90 for 4-10 hectares. The percentage distribution shows that 30% of overall land use falls into the smallest category, 47.5% in the middle, and 22.5% in the largest category. This data shows that the majority of land use is within the 1-2-hectare range.

Table no. -5: Farmers based on the size of their land holdings:

Size of land holding of the farmer	Frequency	Percent
Marginal farmer	116	29
Small farmer	192	48
Medium farmer	68	17
Large farmer	24	6

Source: Field Survey

The distribution of farmers according to the size of their landholdings is shown in the table. Farmers are divided into four groups according to this classification: marginal, small, medium, and large. Each category's frequency and percentage are given, revealing that small farmers comprise the largest group with 192 people (48%), followed by marginal farmers with 116 people (29%). Large farmers are the least represented, with only 24 (6%), while medium farmers make up 68 (17%). According to this data, most farmers own comparatively tiny amounts of land.

Table no. -6: Distribution of crops grown during different seasons:

Name of the cultivation	Frequency	Percent
Kharif	278	69.5
Both kharif and Rabi	122	30.5

Source: Field Survey

The frequency distribution and percentage of various cultivation periods are shown in the table. The two categories it uses to classify farming are "Kharif" and "Both Kharif and Rabi."

Plants are cultivated more frequently during the "Kharif" season (278), which accounts for 69.5% of the total, than during the "Kharif and Rabi" seasons (122, which accounts for 30.5% of the total). The frequency of seasonal agricultural techniques is revealed by this data.

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications:

The study's findings indicate that the majority of respondents were middle-aged, Hindu, and OBC/SEBC. Their houses were mostly semi-pucca. Based on the extent of their land holdings, the majority of respondents were small farmers, owned property ranging from one to two acres, and made agriculture their primary vocation. Most farmers grow their crops during the kharif season, which spans the Rabi and Kharif seasons. These results demonstrate the agricultural and socioeconomic conditions of the farming community under study. By comprehending the socioeconomic traits of farmers, more appropriate policies, such as assistance for income insurance and improvements to market structure, can be put into place.

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